

INTERLACE
RESTORING URBAN ECOSYSTEMS
RECUPERANDO ECOSISTEMAS URBANOS

Communications Toolkit

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Cover Image-Chemnitz

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1 Introduction

This document provides guidance on how to use the various branded templates and other communication materials made available for the INTERLACE project – known collectively as the **Communications Toolkit**.

The Toolkit is designed to assist project partners in communicating about the project to stakeholders and wider audiences. It contains a range of ready-made ingredients for producing high quality materials that convey the project's brand identity or 'personality'. By using the templates and other resources contained in the Toolkit, we can help to make sure that INTERLACE communications are always clear, consistent and engaging. This will help our project to become recognised and capture the interest of the different audiences we need to communicate with.

Please note that the Communications Toolkit will be accompanied by a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, which will be made available by month 10 of the project (August 2021). The Plan will provide a framework for communicating with project stakeholders and wider audiences. It will also set out the role of communications in supporting all of the project's Work Packages and their activities (allowing time for specific WP needs to become known). You will be invited to help develop the CDE Plan as part of the INTERLACE agile workflow approach. If any immediate ideas then don't hesitate to get in touch!

This is the first version of the guidance document, which will be updated throughout the life of the project as new communication materials become available. The project Google Drive will always contain the latest version and you'll be notified as updates become available. See folder **06_Templates & communication material**

Contact

- If you have any questions about the Communications Toolkit; or
- If you need any communications materials not yet contained in the Toolkit...

Just ask! We're happy to help anytime.

You can reach the INTERLACE communications team (WP5) by contacting:

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Colombia (COT time)

2 Talking about INTERLACE

INTERLACE seeks to communicate with a wide range of people from different backgrounds – and not all of them will be familiar with concepts such as nature-based solutions. So it's important to keep our communications clear and simple when talking to people about INTERLACE, especially during this early stage of the project.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan will set out recommendations for project messages in detail. For the time being, we suggest using or adapting the following information when introducing the project to stakeholders and wider audiences.

What is INTERLACE?

It is a project to restore nature in cities across Europe and Latin America. It is using nature-based solutions to help solve some of the challenges facing cities in relation to climate change, people's health and wellbeing, economic development, wildlife conservation and more. It provides an opportunity for city authorities, residents, organisations and businesses to work together in new and creative ways - towards a better future for everyone.

Key "selling points" of INTERLACE

When communicating about INTERLACE, it's useful to include some of the following "selling points" of the project. These can be used to capture people's interest and help the project to stand out from other, similar initiatives. You don't need to include all of these selling points in your communications – just try to incorporate those you feel are most relevant to the people you are communicating with:

- **It's a big, ambitious and exciting project that seeks to make a real difference:** The European Commission has provided €5 million / \$6 million funding across 6 cities, over 4 years, involving 21 leading organisations, all with a passion for helping people and nature.
- **It's about improving people's lives** and creating cities that are greener, cleaner, more liveable, enjoyable and prosperous.
- **It's an open project with a focus on real collaboration:** everyone is welcome to get involved in shaping the project's direction, activities and end results – making sure the project achieves real impact.
- **It's about shared learning between Europe, Latin America and beyond:** drawing upon the wealth of knowledge, experience and good practice in both regions of the world – identifying the challenges we share and developing solutions, together.
- **It's about empowering cities to do more with what they have:** helping local governments restore nature in cities in ways that respond to communities' needs and challenges, but without placing undue demands on finance and resources – becoming smarter and more sustainable.

3 Using the INTERLACE brand

The INTERLACE logo is intended to be an eye-catching and modern design that reflects the core purpose of the project: an 'INTERLACE' of collaboration between Europe and Latin America. It helps to differentiate the INTERLACE from more traditional brands found in the environmental sector – helping the project to stand out and attract attention.

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Please note that a separate brand will be developed for the INTERLACE Innovation Hub. The Hub brand will take inspiration from the project brand and may even follow the same design, but using a different presentation style. This work is in development and partners will be invited to share their ideas soon!

The thinking behind the brand

The shape conveys the idea of interlinking and 'interlacing'.

Circles and spirals are commonly found in ancient Latin American and European art.

The outer, middle and inner circles at each end of the design represent the six cities.

The two focus points represent the relative positions of Europe and Latin America when viewed on an atlas.

3.1 The logo

The INTERLACE logo is made up of two main elements: the **symbol** and the **logotype**. The symbol and logotype should always be used in the proportions shown.

Visual consistency is an important part of the INTERLACE brand. Always use the original copy of the logo, which is available in the project Google Drive (folder 06) in a full range of formats. If you're unsure of which version to use, the general rule is:

- **For electronic materials** (websites, emails, social media, etc): use the png version of the logo.
- **For printed materials:** use the jpg or eps CMYK version of the logo.

3.2 Logo variations

Full colour

Reversed over solid colour

Mono

Reversed over solid image

Symbol

There are four variations of the logo which can be applied in different contexts:

The full colour version is the preferred version of the logo and should be used whenever possible.

The mono version is for use on documents that will be printed, or photocopied in black and white.

The reversed version is to be used over a colour background or photograph.

The Symbol can be used as a social media icon or as a design element. The symbol should supplement the main logo and not be used as a replacement.

3.3 Brand colours

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 0% M: 58% Y: 98% K: 0%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 240 G: 129 B: 8

 Pantone 151 C

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 0% M: 28% Y: 60% K: 0%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 249 G: 195 B: 118

 Pantone 1355 C

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 0% M: 0% Y: 0% K: 80%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 87 G: 87 B: 87

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 20% M: 98% Y: 62% K: 11%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 183 G: 30 B: 65

 Pantone 193 C

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 0% M: 75% Y: 26% K: 0%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 236 G: 96 B: 131

 Pantone 7423 C

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 79% M: 7% Y: 56% K: 0%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 0 G: 164 B: 137

 Pantone 3285 C

 4 Colour Print / CMYK Values
C: 43% M: 0% Y: 27% K: 0%

 On-Screen RGB Values
R: 158 G: 211 B: 199

 Pantone 337 C

These colours can be achieved using the Pantone Matching System®, from the standard set of four colour printing inks (CMYK) or using on-screen (RGB) values.

Breakdowns of these are shown left.

3.4 Logo minimum size

In Printed Matter

The minimum size at which the logo should be used is:

40mm wide
(in printed matter)

200px wide
(for on-screen use)

For On-Screen Use

This is the smallest size at which the logo (and in particular the logotype) retains a reasonable level of legibility. Displaying the logo any smaller would make it difficult to read.

When displaying the logo on A4-size publications, it is recommended that the logo width be at least 50mm.

3.5 Logo clear space

To ensure that the logo is free from any visual distraction, a minimum amount of space must be maintained around it. This visually separates it from any other graphic elements and typography. This distance is called “clear space”.

The minimum clear space must be the height of the logotype element.

As shown in the diagram left.

Whenever possible, this amount of clear space can be increased for maximum clarity.

Please note: the project Google Drive contains a ready-made version of the logo with the correct clear space already included (see 06_Templates & communication material).

3.6 Logo positioning

The logo should be positioned in the top left or bottom right of documents to ‘anchor’ the contents.

When used online it should be positioned top left, unless the medium does not allow.

As always, these are guidelines and not rules. For example: on promotional items, or exhibition and display materials, it may sometimes be better to position the logo centrally in the middle of the layout. If in doubt, contact the communications team (WP5) for help and advice.

3.7 Working with other brand guidelines

oppla
*Ecosystem services,
nature-based solutions
and natural capital.*

- a community for meeting new clients and partners
- a platform for co-design and collaboration
- a marketplace for products and services
- a crowd-sourced enquiry service
- a hub of practical tools and techniques

@OpplaCommunity
oppla.eu

A proud partner of
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When displaying the INTERLACE logo as part of your organisation's own communications, how and where the logo is displayed will of course be determined by your organisation's own brand guidelines.

Use of the INTERLACE logo in this way will obviously vary from one organisation to the next, so it's important for partners to check their own guidelines or speak with colleagues responsible for branding to ensure correct usage. As always, if you're unsure then contact the INTERLACE communications team (WP5) and we'll be happy to help.

Example shown here of the INTERLACE logo being used as part of an event display, created by Oppla.

3.8 Don't do this!

1

4

2

5

3

6

It is important for the INTERLACE logo to be used correctly. Not doing so will weaken the brand and may make the project appear disorganised and unprofessional.

Never:

- 1 Distort the logo dimensions
- 2 Adjust the colours
- 3 Use any other typeface
- 4 Rotate the logo at any angle
- 5 Use on a background where there is little or no contrast. The reversed version must be used in this instance.
- 6 Impose any graphic device around the logo.

3.9 Using the logo as a silhouette

The INTERLACE logo symbol can be used as a silhouette for displaying photographs and other imagery. This is especially appropriate when wanting to add variety and texture to a design; or when linking the brand with a particular place, topic, organisation, activity, etc. It creates a “window’ through which different aspects of the project can be viewed and highlighted.

When using the symbol as a silhouette, it is recommended that single images be used to help ensure clarity.

IMPORTANT: this application of the symbol should never be used to replace the logo itself.

3.10 Typography

Public Sans Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

& ? ! @ / £ € \$ + - - — () , . ; : ‘ “

0123456789

A selection of recommended weights and styles from the Public Sans Family

Extra Light *Extra Light Italic*

Medium *Medium Italic*

Light *Light Italic*

Bold ***Bold Italic***

Regular *Regular Italic*

Extra Bold ***Extra Bold Italic***

Body text

When possible, any materials produced on behalf of the project should be consistent in terms of font usage and typography.

Typography is an important part of the INTERLACE brand and when used correctly helps to unify the appearance of communications. This may not be possible when incorporating the brand in materials produced by partners (where their own brand guidelines will take priority), but it should apply in all cases where INTERLACE is the primary brand.

The typeface used for body copy (as used here) is **Public Sans**.

Various weights and styles can be used for emphasis.

Public Sans is an Open Source font and can be downloaded free from the GoogleFonts website:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Public+Sans>

3.10 Typography

Rubik Medium

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

& ? ! @ / £ € \$ + - - - () , . ; : ' " "

0123456789

A selection of recommended weights and styles from the Rubik Family

Light	<i>Light Italic</i>	Semi Bold	<i>Semi Bold Italic</i>
Regular	<i>Regular Italic</i>	Bold	<i>Bold Italic</i>
Medium	<i>Medium Italic</i>	Extra Bold	<i>Extra Bold Italic</i>

Headings

A secondary typeface has also been selected to work well alongside Public Sans.

This is called **Rubik** and is illustrated left.

It is recommended this is used where more impact is required for headings, pull-out quotes, call-to-actions and website buttons.

Rubik is an Open Source font and can be downloaded free from the GoogleFonts website:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Rubik>

3.10 Typography

Arial Regular

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

& ? ! @ / £ € \$ + - - — () , . ; : ‘ “

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A selection of recommended weights and styles from the Arial Family

Regular

Italic

Bold

Bold Italic

Microsoft Templates

The font Arial has been selected for use with INTERLACE-branded Microsoft Word templates (e.g. Word and PowerPoint).

Arial is a universal font that does not need to be downloaded. Documents and presentations using Arial can be easily edited and shared with third parties, such as project stakeholders.

Arial should not be used in 'designed' communication materials, which should always use the Public Sans and Rubic fonts. Contact the team in WP5 for advice when designing any new materials using the INTERLACE brand.

3.11 Use of photos

Photographs are one of the most important elements of the INTERLACE brand — more important even than the logo when communicating with the public.

Research has shown that people’s attention is immediately drawn to photographs and other images when browsing information, much more so than to text. We also make very quick and sometimes subconscious decisions based on what we see. Hence the phrase “a picture paints a thousand words”.

It’s therefore crucial for any photographs used by the project to be as engaging and high quality as possible. We want people to be captivated by what they see and compelled to find out more...

We will be creating a photo library of high quality images as part of the Communications Toolkit — and we’ll notify you as soon as it’s available. If you have any photographs that you’d like to share and contribute, then please get in touch!

3.12 Photo credits

Granollers - Bob Williams

The project Google Drive contains a library of photos that you are welcome to use - see **folder 08**.

Photo credits should ideally be placed directly on or next to the image. If this is not possible, consider adding a Photo Credit section or page in your document.

Photo credits should include the photographer's name and/or organisation. A short description of what the photo is showing (known as a caption) can also be included, but only if the image needs explaining.

Photo credits should also be included with images used on social media, where the credit or caption can feature in the text of social media posts. When reposting an image on social media, you should also credit the source of the image and seek permission if using it in a different context - for example, if using a photo from Facebook on Twitter.

IMPORTANT: always check permissions of use when obtaining images from third parties - and always check that images showing closeups of people have the necessary 'image release' rights (especially photos of children). If you are unsure, don't use it.

3.13 Photo guidance

Too contrived

Natural

No focal point

Good composure

Too posed

Action shot

Poor quality

Good quality

Keep it real

Avoid photos that appear overly contrived or 'staged'. The INTERLACE brand is all about being real and authentic, so try to use photos that are as natural as possible.

Provide a focus

Always make sure that photos are well composed and capture what you are trying to say. If your photo has a particular subject that you want to draw attention to, then make sure it's in focus and catches the viewer's attention.

Capture the action

When displaying photos of people, try to ensure they are shown doing something rather than being static. Active photos 'say more' and help viewers connect better with the subject.

Convey quality

We want to portray INTERLACE as being a high quality project, so make sure the photos you use are also of the highest quality.

This applies to both the subject matter and the quality or resolution of the photo itself.

Always aim for crisp, clear photos that portray the project at its best.

3.14 Acknowledging the European Commission

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 887396.

It is important to properly acknowledge the European Commission as project funder on all communication materials produced by INTERLACE (this does not apply to materials produced by partners using their own branding).

We have created an 'EC acknowledgement graphic' to make this as easy as possible. Simply download the graphic from the project Google Drive (folder 06) and include it as part of any INTERLACE-branded communications – it is usually positioned at the bottom of a document's final page.

If you need the graphic in a different size or format – no problem! Just get in touch with the communications team (WP5) and we will create a version to fit your needs.

3.15 Using social media

Talking about INTERLACE on social media will help to raise awareness of the project and ultimately help us to reach new audiences and build a strong community.

Please consider the other sections of this Toolkit when talking about INTERLACE on social media. You're likely to engage a wide range of people from different backgrounds, so it's important to keep messages clear, simple and consistent.

It's also important to properly acknowledge the European Commission as project funder where possible, but we recognise this will not be possible on every social media post or image! For example - it's sufficient to occasionally mention that the project is "funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme".

Follow INTERLACE on Twitter at:
@INTERLACE_NBS

Social media tips

- Tag @INTERLACE_NBS and relevant partner social media accounts in your posts.
- Link to the INTERLACE website where possible so followers can learn more about the project.
- Include an image in your post. Social media posts containing an image or video generate much more engagement on average.
- Make sure images you share are the correct aspect ratio for the platform you're using. The recommended aspect ratio for an image posted on Twitter is: 16:9
- Follow other relevant accounts to learn what's working for them and to get inspiration.
- Use existing hashtags such as #NatureBasedSolutions to help relevant posts reach new audiences. Don't use too many hashtags in one post as this can reduce engagement by making your post #Cluttered and #HardToRead
- Build relationships by crediting and tagging other organisations and accounts. For example, if you want to share a great new report make sure you tag the original author.
- Build a community by liking, replying to and sharing other people's posts. On Twitter you can "quote retweet" to add context to your followers when sharing others' posts.
- Ensure your posts are varied and not too repetitive –using different forms of media and post formats.

3.16 Environmental care

The INTERLACE brand is rooted in environmental care and wherever possible this must be reflected in the materials we use for producing communications.

When considering the design brief for materials, it is therefore important to also consider sustainability issues.

All printed material should be produced using environmentally-responsible methods and aim to use recycled and uncoated paper. Quantities of materials and the locality of print companies should also be considered to reduce the carbon footprint.

Paper where possible should be 100% recycled: the minimum requirement should be no less than 50% recycled and 50% from managed forests (FSC accredited) Where possible uncoated.

Print companies should use some or all of these processes:

- Computer-to-plate origination
- Waterless press capacity
- Alcohol-free printing process
- Inks should be vegetable based
- Where possible the finish should be uncoated

Print companies should have accreditation in one or more of the following:

- FSC, carbon neutral status
- ISO 14001
- EMAS (European Ecomanagement & Audit Scheme)
- WPA (Waterless Printing Association)

It is preferable for print companies to be located close to the point of delivery.

3.17 Guidance on file formats

JPEG (.jpg)

(Joint Photographic Experts Group)

JPEG images are commonly used for web graphics, Microsoft Word, Publisher or similar report style documents. The quality of a JPEG file may be suitable for professional printing, although other file formats such as TIF and EPS often provide a better option, particularly when 'high-resolution' (high quality) materials are required.

TIFF (.tiff)

(Tagged Image File Format)

A high-quality graphics format often used for photographs. TIFF format images typically have a large file size and should only really be used for high quality materials that are being professionally printed.

PNG (.png)

(Portable Network Graphic)

One of the best formats for use online (the alternative being JPEG). PNG images are supported by all web browsers and offer good balance between image quality and file size.

GIF (.gif)

(Graphical Interchange Format)

GIFs are a common format for web graphics, especially animated images. PNG are usually a better option when displaying single images.

EPS / PDF (.eps/ .pdf)

(Encapsulated Post Script)

EPS and PDF versions of the INTERLACE logo can be used by designers that have access to the relevant software (e.g. Adobe Creative Suite). This file format should be used in preference to other options when sending materials to be produced by a professional printer.

4 Branded templates

A number of ready-made templates are available for use by partners in creating communication materials on behalf of the project — for example, reports, presentations, consultation and publicity materials, displays and exhibitions.

These templates are contained in the Communications Toolkit, which is available in the project Google Drive - **folder 06_Templates & communication material**

Please note that the Communications Toolkit is in development and will continue to expand with new resources throughout the life of the project. If you need any templates or materials specific to your activities then just let us know and we'll create whatever you need!

4.1 Report template

The INTERLACE report template is available in Microsoft Word format. There is also a simpler Google Docs template, which we recommend using when working on draft documents with input from others.

The report template should be used for producing reports (e.g. project deliverables and internal documents) and is not intended for use in creating publicity materials, which require a more engaging format.

The templates features several key elements of the brand, including the logo, colour palette, typeface and brand graphics.

It includes numerous ready-made Styles for document formatting, applicable to headings, captions, tables and more.

4.2 Presentation template

The INTERLACE presentation template is available in Microsoft PowerPoint format. There is also a Google Slides version.

It features a title slide with headline image, accompanied by a general purpose content slide and examples of alternative layouts that can be adapted as required by the user.

The presentation template uses the standard font Arial. This is so that presentations can be easily edited and shared with third parties, such as project stakeholders.

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